

Traditional Fermented Foods and Beverages of Dimasa Tribe of Dima Hasao District, Assam

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Fermented foods are prepared by the ethnic people of Dima Hasao District, Assam using their traditional knowledge from using plants and animals based raw materials. In the present study, 13 different types of fermented foods and alcoholic beverages were collected from different area of Dima hasao District viz Haflong, Dehangi, Diham, Raze, Sambudhan Raze, Thaisaling Hawar, Lodhi and Lungkok. Most of the fermented foods are prepared from the locally available bamboo shoot, *Cucumis sativus*, *Colocasia sp*, *Zingiber officinale* and *Phyllanthus emblica*, sticky and non-sticky *Oryza sativa* and some animal based sources. The commonly used traditional food and beverages are *Umzang*, *Thagong balai*, *Miya Mikhri*, *Thaishum*, *Hajing*, *Hamlaitai*, *Honohain garain*, *Mesaphain garain*, *Ju-Dima*, *Ju-Gap*, *Ju-Haro*, *Ju-Maihadi* and *Ju-Gra*. The techniques of fermenting different food materials are skillfully performed by the indigenous tribal population to transform food into delicacies by adding flavors and aromas. The modes of consumption, nutritional as well as medicinal uses were also documented in the present study.

Key words: Fermented food, *Umzang*, *Thagong balai*, *Miya Mikhri*, *Thaishum*, *Hajing*, *Hamlaitai*,